

FOUR-IN-BLEND: AN INSTRUCTIONAL STRATEGY IN TEACHING BIOLOGY TO GRADE 12 SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Four-in-Blend: An Instructional Strategy in Teaching Biology to Grade 12 Senior High School Students

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Abstract

To address the needs of today's millennial and centennial learners, blended learning strategies, such as laboratory rotation, station rotation, blended cycle, and flipped classroom, were integrated with technology, collaborative learning, and traditional face-to-face instruction. This mixed-method, quasi-experimental study, involving 42 Grade 12 students from a public Senior High School during the 2019-2020 school year, aimed to assess their performance in biology. Students were paired and divided into experimental and control groups based on their Earth Science averages. Over a 7-week period, the study progressed through pre-experimental, experimental, and post-experimental stages. Using a validated instrument, the pretest scores of both groups showed no significant difference, indicating similar capacities before the intervention. However, after the intervention, both groups demonstrated improvement in General Biology, with the experimental group—exposed to the four blended learning methods—achieving significantly higher posttest scores than the control group, which followed traditional teaching. Students in the experimental group reported that blended learning was engaging, promoted independent and collaborative learning, catered to diverse intelligences, sparked interest, and provided personalized, contextualized, and convenient instruction. Overall, blended learning was found to enhance learning opportunities effectively.

Keywords: *blended cycle, blended learning, collaborative learning, flipped classroom, lab rotation*

Introduction

Today's learners, including Millennials and Generation Z (Centennials), exhibit distinct traits compared to previous generations. According to Gilbert (2011) Millennials are well-educated, tech-savvy, confident, and skilled at multitasking, while Centennials are more independent, entrepreneurial, and better multitaskers (Patel, 2017). Both generations were born and have grown up in a digital era, are adept at using technology and continuously adapting to new systems, which may contribute to their ability to multitask effectively in digital environments (Mark, et al., 2014; Kosterlitz & Lewis, 2017). In the Philippines, Filipino children spend significant time on social media. Filipinos spent an average of 4 hours and 17 minutes per day on social media sites such as Facebook, Snapchat and Twitter. The data were based on active monthly user data from social media companies

Expanding this, Centennials are considered "intensified" versions of Millennials, as they are digital natives with higher expectations and a stronger focus on individuality. Both generations prefer meaningful, context-driven learning and have short attention spans (Sharma, 2016). The long hours of discussion and teacher-centered approach may not always suffice for learning to take place among this kind of generation. They want more in class, they need interaction, and they need to be involved. As responded in the study of Abdulbaki, et al (2018), there must be a good opportunity to interact during the discussion and that the lecturer is not the sole authority in class.

Giving this set of learners long lectures, and less varied activities in a way, traditional teaching methods become less effective. This is evident in the result of standardized tests. The DepEd reported that the NAT mean percentage score (MPS) for Grade 10 high school in school year 2017-2018 was 31.26 in Science in the National level, and 31.13 in Region VI. Furthermore, the Grade 10 NAT of Oton National High School in the same year was 36.81. Furthermore, During the Learning Action Cell (LAC) session of the Science Department dated May 2019, Science teachers assigned in Grade 11 and grade 12 shared their problems and observations in their Science class. It was found out that teachers experienced common problem in terms of students' low motivation in class, and the frequent use of mobile phones during classes. As mentioned by Duffy and Elwood, (2013) the context of the classroom, including peer relationships and pedagogical methods, plays a crucial role in student engagement. Millennials prefer collaborative learning experiences, quick feedback, and have low tolerance for boredom.

For example, slides filled with text can overwhelm students, causing them to take notes in an attempt to keep up, which can be counterproductive to their learning experience (Felder & Brent, 2005). Xiao and Sugiura (2013) also added that too much text on slides distracts students, reducing engagement and interaction with the lecturer. In these scenarios, technology was integrated but engagement was still less. Many web-based learning instruction fail to incorporate principles of effective teaching and learning. Researches have shown that the greatest improvement in learners' learning process occurs when online courses also involve some in-class learning (Means, Toyama, Murphy, & Bakia, 2010). This claim was also supported by De Jong et al. (2018), Technologies like simulations and online labs are effective when combined with other instructional approaches such as direct instruction and embedded instructional support.

Price, a Dalton State College psychology professor suggested that millennial want more variety in class as mentioned in the work of Trembach and Deng (2018). Optimizing learning outcomes, self-paced learning, combined with the best of technology and teacher assisted learning can help increase classroom engagement and motivation among learners. Maxwell and White (2017) emphasized the

modification in blended learning types in order to cater the needs of today's generation. It is apparent that combining technology in teachers' discussion coupled with self-paced, and collaborative learning is relevant among millennials and centennials making them the active entity in the entire learning process (Sharma, 2016).

Synthesizing the discussion given above, it can be ascertained that blending in-person learning with technology can maximize student engagement and improve learning outcomes. This combination leverages the strengths of both methods: the interactivity of face-to-face instruction and the accessibility of digital tools. The study seeks to explore how blended learning can improve students' performance and experiences in teaching biology at Oton National High School, addressing the educational needs of Millennials and Centennials. The goal is to create a more engaging, technology-integrated learning environment.

Research Questions

The study aimed to determine the effect of blended learning in students' performance in Biology when compared to conventional learning among Grade 12 students of Oton National High School, Oton, Iloilo during the first semester of the school year 2019 - 2020. Specifically, the study seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the learners' level of performance in biology before the exposure to four-in-blend and after exposure to four-in-blend?
2. What is the level of performance in biology of the four-in-blend and conventional group after the intervention?
3. Is there a significant difference between the posttest mean scores of four-in-blend and conventional group?
4. Is there a significant difference between the pretest and posttest mean scores of the four-in-blend group?

Methodology

Research Design

This quasi-experimental study used a pretest-posttest control group design to assess the impact of blended learning, in particular the four common types of blended learning on students' performance in biology. Two groups of Grade 12 students at Oton National High School were studied—one exposed to blended learning, the other to conventional teaching methods. The students were pre-assigned by class and matched according to their academic performance in Earth Science.

Instrument

The following instruments were used in the conduct of the study:

The Summative Test. This was a researcher – made test which was anchored to the Curriculum Guide for the Senior High School Grade 12 General Biology 1 provided by the Department of Education. This was used to determine the effect of blended learning on the performance of Grade 12 Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics students in General Biology 1. The lessons covered seven topics in the first quarter of the School Year 2019-2020. The topics included were Cell Theory, Cell Organelles, Prokaryotes and Eukaryotes, Plant and Animal Cells, Cell Membrane Structure, Cell Transport, and Cell Modification.

The summative test was composed of 50 multiple-choice items. This was subjected to content-and-face validation by biology experts. The initial draft of the test had 80 items. It was pilot tested to First Year Medical Technology Students of the University of San Agustin who have taken general biology 1 during their senior high school. The data gathered from the pilot testing were subjected to reliability test using Kuder Richardson 20 (KR-20) Test for reliability. The initial 80 – item was cut down to 50 item multiple choice type of test which had a reliability coefficient of 0.73. Of the 50 total number of test items, 15 items belonged to Remembering, 19 were comprehension questions, 10 belonged to analysis, and 6 were application questions.

Lesson Plan. Seven detailed lesson plans which corresponded to 7 different topics in the first quarter of the school year 2019-2020 were prepared for the entire duration of the experiment. It was divided into two columns, one of which was for the blended learning and the other column was for the conventional learning.

The blended learning lesson plan was made to have the blend of teacher initiated instruction, using computer (offline videos) discussion, collaborative work and self-paced learning. The lessons included were Cell Theory, Cell Organelles, Prokaryotes and Eukaryotes, Plant and Animal Cell, Cell Membrane Structure, Cell Transport, and Cell Modification. Four kinds of blended learning were utilized. Lab Rotation, Station Rotation, Blended Cycle, and Flipped Classroom Discussion.

In the Cell Theory, Lab Rotation was utilized. The Lab Rotation, allowed students to rotate through stations on a fixed schedule. Offline videos were pre downloaded and installed in a computer lab. Teacher initiated instruction is done in the classroom. The students were asked to proceed to a computer laboratory for them to view the offline videos. Then collaborative work was done to deepen the discussion. It was followed by clearing up of misconceptions by the teacher. The same Lab Rotation was utilized for the delivery of cell organelles.

For the discussion of prokaryotes and eukaryotes, Station Rotation was used. In Station Rotation students rotated from one station to another. The stations consist of the input and output stations. In the input stations, there were offline video station, an online station (internet is provided), and reading station. The input stations were conducted in the computer laboratory. The other stations consist of

the output stations. In the output stations, the students answered multiple choice questions, a drawing station (the students sketch prokaryotes and eukaryotes), and an open-ended questions (essay).

In the discussion of plant and animal cells and cell modification, blended cycle was utilized. This is adopted from the blended cycle described by Paul Anderson Bozeman Science (2012). Blended Cycle moves through the following steps. First, the students were asked of a question which served as a motivation. Second, the students were asked to investigate on some characteristics. Then, an offline video was used for enrichment. Elaboration was done through group activity. An evaluation through a quiz then followed.

In the discussion of Cell Membrane Structure and Cell Transport, Flipped Classroom was utilized. The Flipped Classroom model flips the traditional relationship between class time and homework. Students learned at home via videos that were uploaded in the Blended closed group page in Facebook. Guide questions were also given on the said group page. The teacher used class time for teacher-guided practice.

Procedure

The data-gathering procedure was conducted in three stages: pre-experimental stage, experimental stage, and post – experimental stage.

Pre-experimental stage. A permit to study was secured by the researcher and a letter was sent to the principal asking permission to use the first year Medical Technology Students of the University of San Agustin to be the respondents of reliability test of the instruments. Another letter was given to the principal of Oton National High School for the conduct of the study and the permission for the Grade 12 Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics Students to be the respondents for the conduct of the study.

This study consisted of two groups: experimental and control groups. The choice of whether a certain group was subjected to blended learning or the conventional method was made through toss-coin technique.

Experimental stage. The experimental group was exposed to blended learning which were a combination of teacher-initiated instruction, computer or technology use, collaborative work, and self-paced learning. The study utilized different kinds of blended learning such as lab rotation, rotation, flipped classroom, and blended cycle.

A day after the pretest was given to both groups, the researcher who is herself the one who taught for both blended and conventional groups, immediately started the treatment for the experimental group and teaching the other group conventionally. The six-week experimental stage of the study started on July 1, 2019, and ended on August 9, 2019. The researcher taught the blended group at 7:30 am to 8:30 am, followed by the conventional group at 8:30 to 9:30 am.

Classroom observation by the selected science teachers of the same school was required to ensure that the lesson plans were followed correctly. The teacher observer was given a checklist during the observation as a guide. The teacher observer gave ratings, comments, and suggestions immediately after each class session. The teacher observers also had random informal interviews among the students exposed to intervention. Their observations were noted.

The group which was exposed to blended learning was asked to write a journal about their experiences during the intervention stage. They were asked to write a journal in every topic discussed. This was done in order to see the themes of the students experience towards blended learning. This is done to support the quantitative result after the experiment.

On the second week of the intervention, the panel members conducted a one day face validation and classroom observation, which was on July 13, 2019. This was done to ensure the correctness of the delivery of the lesson and the implementation of the blended learning. After the said face validation, corrective feedback was given. The panel members gave valuable suggestions for the improvement and proper delivery of the blended learning intervention.

Post-experimental Stage. After the intervention period, posttest was administered both to the experimental group and the conventional groups. The students took the summative test to determine the performance in General Biology 1 on August 20, 2019. They were given an hour to answer the test. The result of the test was subjected to statistical analysis.

The students who were exposed to blended learning were asked to write about their experience on blended learning during the experimental stage. The journal entry of each student was encoded and was analyzed through thematic analysis. The themes were used to support the result of the quantitative data. These themes discussed the perception of the students towards blended learning.

Data Analysis

The data gathered were subjected to statistical analyses. Both descriptive and inferential statistics utilized the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences Software. The following statistical tools were employed in the analysis of the data to be obtained.

Descriptive Statistics. Mean was used to describe the pretest and posttest performance of the Grade 12 Learners who were exposed to blended learning and the other group who received the conventional method of teaching.

The standard deviation was used to describe how the pretest and posttest performance of the group that was exposed to blended learning and the other group that received the conventional method.

Inferential Statistics. The t-test for independent samples was used to compare the means of the pretest and posttest of those exposed to blended learning and those exposed to conventional method. This test was used in order to see whether there is a significant difference between the mean scores of those exposed to blended learning and those exposed to conventional method.

The t-test for dependent samples was used to see whether a change or a difference in means of those exposed to blended learning before and after the intervention existed. The same is done to those who were taught to conventional method before and after the intervention. This was used to see whether there is a significant difference between the mean scores before and after the intervention.

Ethical Considerations

In the conduct of this research, the researcher secured permission and approval from the school's administration, and the department of education division office. Student participants were given orientation about the details and the purpose of the research study and proper orientation was done before the study. The parents of the respondents were given a letter and notified of the intervention schedule. Further, they were given information on the benefits that their children get from the proposed research study. Furthermore, the use of gadgets was a necessity in the conduct of the study; parents were also informed. Formal letters were secured to all concerned individuals before the conduct of the study. Scores and all the responses of the participants were recorded accordingly, documented, and kept confidential by the researcher. All materials that were purchased were secured with official receipts and duly reported with truthfulness in the statement of accounts and expenses.

Results and findings of the study were reported with clarity, verity, and honesty. All student participants, school administrator, teachers, and parents were informed and notified with the results and findings of the study. Student participants were recognized during the card day and were given certificates of recognition together with their parents for showing their cooperation in the implementation of the research study.

Results and Discussion

Level of performance in organismal biology before and after exposure to four-in-blend

The performance of the blended group before the intervention was satisfactory, with a mean score of 20 (SD = 3.72). After exposure to the intervention, the group's performance significantly improved, as reflected in the increased mean score of 34 (SD = 4.61). The intervention involved four common types of blended learning: s lab rotation, station rotation, blended learning cycle, and flipped classroom discussion. This improvement indicates that the experimental group, which was exposed to the intervention, outperformed their previous performance. The increase in scores highlights the positive impact of blended learning on the group's overall achievement. This can be attested to the fact that millennials and centennials learn in different ways since they have different learning styles. Significantly, they are tech-savvy. Making things relevant to the students was manifested by employing technology in teaching can cater to their needs and enhance the learning process (Oomen-Early & Early, 2015).

Table 1. *Performance in biology prior and after the exposure to four-in-blend*

<i>Four-in-Blend</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
Pretest	21	20.47	3.72	Satisfactory
Posttest	21	34.05	4.61	Outstanding

Scale and Description: 32.5 – 40.0 Outstanding; 24.5 – 32.4 Very Satisfactory; 16.5 – 24.4 Satisfactory; 8.5 – 16.4 Fairly Satisfactory; and 01.0 – 8.4 Poor

Level of performance in organismal biology of the four-in-blend and conventional group after the intervention

The four-in-blend group achieved an outstanding mean score (M = 34.05, SD = 4.61), while the conventional group attained a satisfactory mean score (M = 26.95, SD = 5.13). The standard deviations of both groups suggest variability in the posttest scores, with differences observed between learners exposed to blended learning and those following conventional methods. The descriptive data reveals a higher mean score in the four-in-blended group than the conventional group, indicating a notable increase in achievement among the four-in-blend group. The increased scores suggest that blended learning can be an effective method for enhancing student learning and engagement. In any type of blended learning utilized, the opportunity for students to do things on their own was emphasized. This is affirmed in the works of Scheiter (2014), Aljafari (2019), and Olajide (2023) that self-paced learning provides learners with the freedom to control the pace, sequence, and selection of learning materials. In the study, the students were given offline videos to be viewed at their own pace and time. Students vary in learning pace, the offline videos helped them view and review any time they want. Thus, fostering autonomy and individualized learning experiences.

Table 2. *Four-in-blend and conventional groups' performance in organismal biology after the intervention*

<i>Group</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
Blended	21	34.05	4.61	Outstanding
Conventional	21	26.95	5.13	Very Satisfactory

Scale and Description: 32.5 – 40.0 Outstanding; 24.5 – 32.4 Very Satisfactory; 16.5 – 24.4 Satisfactory; 8.5 – 16.4 Fairly Satisfactory; and 01.0 – 8.4 Poor

Difference between two-in-blend and conventional groups' performance in organismal biology after the intervention

A significant difference was found between the posttest mean scores of the two groups, as indicated by $t(40) = 4.713$, $p < .05$. Consequently, the null hypothesis, which stated that there is no significant difference between the posttest mean scores of the two groups, is rejected. The data also shows that the 7.095-point difference in the posttest means between the Blended Group and the Conventional Group is significant at the 0.05 alpha level. This suggests that the teaching method used with the experimental group had a significant impact on their increased achievement in Biology.

The results indicate that using the four blended learning methods significantly enhanced the learners' overall experience. Students were more engaged and challenged by incorporating different blended approaches for each lesson, ensuring their efforts were effectively utilized. Understanding learning styles is crucial since it helps students and educators become more self-aware of their strengths and weaknesses as learners, thus guiding the selection of appropriate teaching strategies (Feldman, et al., 2015). The different types of blended learning employed in the study were seen to be of impact since they utilized technology; made use of small bite information through the use of a search engine; and further the discussions were deepened by teacher-initiated instruction.

Table 3. *Difference in the posttest scores of four-in-blend and conventional group*

Group	n	df	Mean	Mean Difference	t-value	p-value	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
Blended	21	40	31.75	6.31	*4.122	.000	3.18	9.44
Control	21		26.44					

* $p < 0.05$

Difference in the level of performance of the four-in-blend group in biology before and after the intervention

The result reveals that there is a significant difference between the pretest and posttest mean scores of the Blended Group. This is indicated by $t(21) = 11.98$, $p = 0.000 < .05$. The table shows that the difference of 13.57 in the means of the pretest-posttest scores of the Blended Group was significant at 0.05 alpha level.

The four types of blended learning played a key role in the positive outcomes of the intervention. Addressing the needs of today's learners, the integration of technology and collaborative work proved effective in managing the learning process. By incorporating reflective, creative, and collaborative approaches, this method tackles common challenges faced by millennials, such as difficulties with concentration, engagement, and socialization (Karakas et al., 2015).

Their engagement in the use of technology such as mobile phone and computer during the intervention stage was relevant to what they can enjoy and interest. They were observed to participate in the learning process actively. Clark and Mayer (2011) articulated—multimedia presentations can encourage learners to engage in active learning.

Table 4. *Difference in the pretest - posttest scores of the four-in-blend group*

Blended Group	n	df	Mean	Mean Difference	t-value	p-value	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
Before	21	40	20.48	13.57	*11.98	.000	11.21	15.93
After	21		34.05					

* $p < 0.05$

Conclusions

This research aimed to determine the effectiveness of the four-in-blend utilizing the four common types of blended learning; lab rotation, station rotation, blended cycle, and flipped classroom in teaching Biology among the Grade 12 Senior High School Learners of Oton National High School in the School Year 2019-2020.

This quasi-experimental pretest-posttest control group was used among Grade 12 students of Oton National High School, Oton, Iloilo during the second semester of the school year 2019 - 2020.

The following were the findings of the study:

Performance prior to the intervention

The level of performance of the four-in blend group prior to the intervention was satisfactory. After the intervention, there was an increase in the scores and was described based on the scale to be outstanding.

Performance after the intervention

The level of performance in organismal biology of the four-in-blend and conventional group after the intervention varies. The four-in-blend group's level of performance was outstanding as indicated in the scale. While the conventional group's mean was satisfactory.

Significant difference between posttest mean scores of the two groups

There is a significant difference between the posttest mean scores of four-in-blend and conventional group.

Significant difference between the pretest and posttest of the four-in-blend group

There is a significant difference between the pretest and posttest mean scores of the four-in-blend group

The result shows that after exposure to the intervention, the blended group performed better in terms of achievement in General Biology 1. It is further concluded that the four in blend learning is an effective and innovative instructional strategy. Knowing the characteristics of the millennials and the centennials, this innovative strategy can motivate students to learn and perform better in general biology. Catering their needs can provide a positive teaching-learning environment. Blended learning can therefore be used to maximize today's generation's learning experience.

Implications for Theory

The aforementioned findings and conclusions have led to certain implications as regard to the increased achievement in a content-rich subject like General Biology.

In the preparation of the instructional process, teachers are encouraged to consider the incorporation of offline videos, podcasts, and technology. This is supported by the multimedia principle. Mayer (1947), states that —people learn more deeply from words and pictures than from words alone. The lesson in Biology, which is a content-rich subject, needs to be delivered with visuals and auditory procedures to ensure learning to take place.

On the same light, the learners need to be exposed to activities that will make them the —active entity in the learning process. As supported by the same principle, multimedia principle, learning cannot be achieved by putting words to pictures or pictures to words. Students actively create mental representations of the information given to them. By exposing them to activities, that they themselves perform, learning will actively take place. This is affirmed in the classic theory of learning by doing John Dewey (1938) and more recently David Kolb (1984).

The study has also an implication to the teacher's role in integrating teaching and learning environment, the teacher should assist students with making connections in order for students to find meaning in the learning process. Making this process a reality, means that education should be student centered. Howard Gardner (1994)states that multiple intelligence theory opens the door to a wide variety of student-centered teaching strategies. It is therefore suggestive for instructions to be varied and differentiated.

Implications for Practice

The result of this study supports the idea that blended learning can be an effective approach in teaching the generations of today, the millennials and the centennials.

Studies have shown that learners of today exhibit different characteristics and potentials compared to the learners before. They are able to multitask, they are digital natives full of energy. With this kind of attribute, learners of today need a new landscape in the teaching-learning process. The researcher utilized the combination of face-to-face learning, and the use of technology, together with self-paced and group activities in learning General Biology. The students exposed to this blended approach had an increased achievement. Reflective on the themes in their journal, the students gained different experiences during the implementation. The experiences were evident of enjoyment, integrating technology, the strength of collaborative learning as well as independent learning have maximized learning opportunities.

The result showed that students enjoyed themselves during the blended learning process.

Enjoyment implies that students are interested in what they do and will allow learning to manifest better. The use of technology such as computers and mobile phones during the intervention has a positive impact on the students. This implies that their being digital natives was catered. Student engagement in collaborative work during the lesson is an indicator of a well-motivated environment which, in the case of the millennials and centennials, should be a need. Blended also allowed them to experience independent learning. Learning alone means learning at their own pace. Self-paced learning is indicative of students owning their learning. This implies that students are given opportunities to generate their ideas.

Prior to the intervention, the researcher planned and asked permission for the school facilities to be used during the application of the intervention. One of the limitations was that, in a normal setting, a computer laboratory is not readily available. It therefore implies that computers are important in the conduct of blended learning. For the successful implementation of any kind of blended learning, the use of a computer is essential. Whether offline videos or the internet is provided, computers should readily be available.

A spacious and well-ventilated classroom is also one of the factors that could bring blended learning implementation at its best. Station rotation to be specific, makes use of input and output stations. These stations demand space and enough ventilation to be conducted well.

Another implication of the study is the role of the teacher. In the new era of education, teachers are considered as facilitators. In this study, the researcher designed activities under the Blended learning that enable students to work at their own and maximize participation. The activities enable them to collaborate with the other students, and gain confidence, and belonging. This implies the teachers' role in designing instructions that will make students active participants in the learning process is a necessity. The teachers

must see the students' needs to facilitate a good learning environment.

The teacher's utilization of Facebook is the easiest and the most convenient platform to cater to today's learners of being digital natives. Almost all of the students today have Facebook accounts. Using Facebook closed groups to upload videos and instructions for assignments can be utilized. It was also observed that flipped classroom discussion through the closed group on Facebook has helped during the limited classroom time. During the conduct of the study, intramurals and other related school activities happened. With the use of a flipped classroom, students can still learn at home and are ready to answer guided questions in school when time permits.

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